

LTO Maintenance Form

Year:
Maintenance Conservation Job No.

Accession No.		Object Title:														
Maintenance (All Staff)		COMMENTS	Schedule↓ Date Done→	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	
✓ Tasks To be Done																
	Check for damage, vandalism, changed condition, rubbish etc		Monthly													
	Dust/vacuum exterior		Monthly													
	Dust/vacuum interior		Monthly													
	Clean windows		Monthly													
	Inspect tie-downs		Monthly													
	Inspect supports		Monthly													
	Inspect for oil leaks		Monthly													
	Measure splits in wood		Monthly													
	Inspect and clean drip trays		Monthly													
	Inspect and change nappies		Monthly													
	Check for pests/hazards		Monthly													
	Check lighting & AV		Monthly													
Maintenance (Conservation Staff)		COMMENTS	Schedule↓ Date Done→	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	
✓ Tasks To be Done																
	Check for corrosion		3 monthly													
	Rotate wheels (5/4 turns forward)		3 monthly													
	Actuate clutch and brake		3 monthly													
	Inspect and charge batteries		3 monthly													
	Check water and oil		3 monthly													
	Start operational engine (note: do not schedule starting old vehicles in winter)		3 monthly													
	Run operational vehicle		3 monthly													
	Check wheels/tracks		6 monthly													
	Rotate propellers		6 monthly													
	Hand crank static engine		6 monthly													
	Sample fluids		6 monthly													
	Check engine coupons (take digital photo)		6 monthly													

	Check and change inhibitors (engine, cooling system, fuel system)		2 yearly												
	Review maintenance plan		2 yearly												